

Fine Dust Pollution in Europe

It grew by an average of 8.5% between 2014 and 2021

The European Innovation Scoreboard calculates the value of emissions into the atmosphere in the manufacturing sector in tons.

Ranking of countries for emissions to air from fine dust in 2021. Switzerland ranks first in terms of emissions to air from fine dust with an amount of 134.60 units, followed by Denmark with an amount of 133.52 units and from Germany with a value of 131.14 units. In the middle of the table there are Finland with an amount of 101.80 units, followed by Hungary with a value of 101.42 units and Spain with a value of 100 units. Latvia, Portugal and Serbia close the ranking with a value of 0.00 units.

Ranking of European countries by percentage change in emissions from fine dust into the air between 2014 and 2021. Luxembourg is in first place for the percentage change in emissions from fine dust with a value of 35.00% or equal to an amount of 24.85 units, followed by Poland with a value of 33.35% equal to an amount of 13.50 units and by Croatia with a value of 22.88% equal to an amount of 14.21 unit. In the middle of the table there are Ireland with an amount of 8.72% equal to an amount of 10.47 units, followed by Spain with a value of 7.29% equal to an amount of 6.79 units, and by the countries Bass with a value of 6.39% equal to an amount of 6.96 units. Bulgaria closes the ranking with a value of -12.91% equal to an amount of -9.30 units, followed by Cyprus with an amount of -23.92% or equal to a variation of -9.62 units and by Serbia with an amount of -100.00% equal to an amount of -8.75 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient was carried out below. The analysis shows the presence of three clusters as indicated below, namely:

- *Cluster 1:* Netherlands, Czech Republic, France, Austria, Ireland, Italy, Sweden, Malta, Germany, Lithuania, Hungary, Denmark, Belgium, Switzerland, Slovakia, Finland, Spain, United Kingdom;
- *Cluster 2:* Portugal, Latvia, Estonia, Serbia;
- *Cluster 3:* Romania, Greece, Croatia, Bulgaria, Iceland, Poland, Norway, Luxembourg, Cyprus, Slovenia.

By calculating the value of the median of the clusters it results that the value of the median C1 is equal to an amount of 116.09 units, followed by the median value of the countries in cluster C3 is equal to an amount of 68.34 units and the median value of C2 equal to 0. It therefore follows that $C1 = 116.09 > C3 = 68.34 > C2 = 0.00$.

However, it should be considered that the countries of Cluster 2 or Portugal, Latvia, Estonia and Serbia have an indicator value of 0. This value must be interpreted. Indeed, it is unlikely that there will be no emissions in these countries. On the other hand, it is much more plausible that these countries have failed to report the level of their emissions. Therefore, the clustering is repeated

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without considering the countries with a zero value of the emission, namely Portugal, Latvia, Estonia and Serbia. The following clusters are therefore produced, namely:

- *Cluster 1*: Bulgaria, Cyprus, Greece, Croatia, Iceland, Luxembourg, Norway, Poland, Romania, Slovenia
- *Cluster 2*: Austria, Belgium, Switzerland, Czech Republic, Germany, Denmark, Spain, Finland, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Malta, Netherlands, Sweden, Slovakia, United Kingdom.

It follows therefore that by calculating the value of the median for cluster 1 and cluster 2. It appears that the median value of cluster 1 is equal to an amount of 68.33 while the value of cluster 2 is equal to 114.68. That is, the countries of cluster 2 have a value of fine dust pollution equal to 1.67 times the countries of cluster 1. The following order is therefore obtained, ie $C2 = 114.68 > C1 = 68.33$.

If we look at the geographical structure, it is possible to verify that the countries of cluster 1, that is the countries with the lowest level of pollution, are located in Eastern Europe. This circumstance may be due to the low industrialization of those countries. A factor that, however, could change, even in the short term, due to the massive phenomenon of relocation of production activities from Western Europe to Eastern Europe.

Network Analysis. The network analysis model is then applied to verify if there are links between the various countries analyzed in terms of emissions. To calculate the presence of links between countries, the dataset is analyzed using Manhattan distances. The dataset is determined as follows:

- Number of nodes 28;
- Number of edges 48;
- Average degree equal to 3,429;
- Density 0.127.

The analysis shows that there is a network between Switzerland, Denmark, Germany and Malta:

- Switzerland is connected to Denmark with a value of 0.34 units;
- Denmark is connected to Switzerland with a value of 0.34 and to Germany with a value of 0.37;
- Germany has a bond with Denmark with a value of 0.37 units and with Malta with a value of 0.29;
- Malta has a connection with Germany of 0.29 units.

A network between Bulgaria, Italy, Sweden and Belgium is also detected with the following values:

- Bulgaria has a link with Italy equal to an amount of 0.47 and with Belgium equal to 0.35;
- Belgium has a bond with Bulgaria equal to 0.35, with Italy equal to 0.45 and with Sweden equal to 0.45;
- Italy has a bond with Bulgaria equal to 0.47, with Belgium equal to 0.45 and with Sweden equal to 0.31;
- Sweden has a bond with Italy equal to 0.31 units and with Belgium equal to 0.45.

In addition, there are the following links between pairs of countries, namely:

- France and the Netherlands are connected with a value of 0.31;
- Spain and Finland relate to a value of 0.46.

Conclusions. In summary, it is possible to verify the presence of an increasing trend of fine dust. On average, between 2014 and 2021, the value of emissions from fine particles increased by an amount equal to 8.54% on average for the countries considered, or equal to an amount of 6.93 units. The analysis of clusters shows that most industrialized countries in Western and Central Europe have a high level of fine particles. It should be considered that this trend contrasts with the economic policies envisaged by the European Union which has adopted an orientation towards environmental sustainability. However, the Russian-Ukrainian conflict is likely to increase pollution since many European countries to cope with the rising price of gas may choose to use less eco-friendly technologies than those that could have been used in the presence. of reduced energy prices.

References

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Emissioni nell'aria da polveri sottili in Europa

Countries	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Austria	★ 117,47	★ 118,92	★ 121,05	★ 123,36	★ 123,73	★ 125,84	★ 126,22	★ 127,80
Belgium	★ 100,48	★ 102,75	★ 105,57	★ 106,14	★ 105,08	★ 105,35	★ 107,34	★ 109,25
Bulgaria	★ 72,01	★ 80,82	★ 77,08	★ 71,59	★ 63,70	★ 59,84	★ 59,80	★ 62,71
Switzerland	★ 131,60	★ 131,73	★ 132,62	★ 132,73	★ 133,81	★ 134,36	★ 134,60	★ 134,60
Cyprus	★ 40,20	★ 70,17	★ 51,31	★ 32,22	★ 33,69	★ 39,22	★ 31,82	★ 30,58
Czechia	★ 106,31	★ 108,41	★ 107,20	★ 108,68	★ 114,82	★ 117,62	★ 120,06	★ 121,93
Germany	★ 128,04	★ 128,11	★ 128,53	★ 129,41	★ 129,50	★ 129,87	★ 130,73	★ 131,14
Denmark	★ 127,72	★ 128,60	★ 130,41	★ 132,34	★ 132,18	★ 132,78	★ 134,13	★ 133,52
Greece	★ 65,61	★ 66,02	★ 66,82	★ 62,43	★ 60,68	★ 63,22	★ 65,76	★ 66,03
Spain	★ 93,21	★ 91,22	★ 99,68	★ 102,40	★ 99,50	★ 100,77	★ 100,79	★ 100,00
Finland	★ 97,04	★ 95,93	★ 99,31	★ 97,88	★ 98,39	★ 97,78	★ 101,36	★ 101,80
France	★ 110,63	★ 111,57	★ 110,43	★ 111,43	★ 110,72	★ 110,57	★ 110,64	★ 111,16
Croatia	★ 62,09	★ 61,51	★ 62,01	★ 66,69	★ 70,04	★ 75,39	★ 73,47	★ 76,30
Hungary	★ 103,45	★ 104,94	★ 107,31	★ 103,92	★ 107,41	★ 106,24	★ 105,99	★ 101,42
Ireland	★ 120,02	★ 121,71	★ 120,68	★ 119,22	★ 129,76	★ 129,34	★ 129,39	★ 130,49
Iceland	★ 55,51	★ 32,58	★ 42,10	★ 47,75	★ 46,11	★ 59,55	★ 63,56	★ 63,56
Italy	★ 100,85	★ 103,81	★ 107,83	★ 108,77	★ 109,16	★ 109,63	★ 110,13	★ 110,55
Lithuania	★ 100,30	★ 98,30	★ 101,07	★ 110,08	★ 116,37	★ 117,58	★ 118,58	★ 120,23
Luxembourg	★ 70,99	★ 72,48	★ 82,13	★ 71,65	★ 84,37	★ 87,95	★ 92,90	★ 95,83
Malta	★ 127,26	★ 126,52	★ 128,63	★ 128,30	★ 128,20	★ 128,54	★ 125,74	★ 125,62
Netherlands	★ 108,86	★ 110,75	★ 110,68	★ 112,23	★ 112,83	★ 113,31	★ 114,33	★ 115,82
Norway	★ 72,52	★ 77,18	★ 76,04	★ 81,24	★ 80,17	★ 81,23	★ 83,15	★ 84,61
Poland	★ 40,48	★ 45,91	★ 43,67	★ 46,70	★ 49,96	★ 53,16	★ 50,25	★ 53,98
Romania	★ 59,93	★ 52,08	★ 59,37	★ 62,97	★ 61,61	★ 64,60	★ 69,61	★ 70,64
Sweden	★ 102,35	★ 102,43	★ 103,10	★ 105,69	★ 109,16	★ 110,12	★ 110,94	★ 111,94
Slovenia	★ 84,32	★ 87,14	★ 84,72	★ 81,77	★ 84,74	★ 87,82	★ 87,28	★ 87,40
Slovakia	★ 92,94	★ 94,11	★ 93,95	★ 100,71	★ 104,80	★ 105,40	★ 106,45	★ 109,88
United Kingdom	★ 94,55	★ 94,48	★ 91,03	★ 89,26	★ 91,37	★ 94,13	★ 93,34	★ 93,23

	2021	Feature 1	Cluster	Silhouette
3	62.7118	Bulgaria	C1	0.667734
5	30.5827	Cyprus	C1	0.666977
9	66.0282	Greece	C1	0.690601
13	76.3012	Croatia	C1	0.684681
16	63.5552	Iceland	C1	0.679846
19	95.8313	Luxembourg	C1	0.6076
22	84.6079	Norway	C1	0.629237
23	53.9782	Poland	C1	0.682871
24	70.6429	Romania	C1	0.691694
26	87.398	Slovenia	C1	0.533101
1	127.803	Austria	C2	0.70366
2	109.255	Belgium	C2	0.693056
4	134.601	Switzerland	C2	0.689618
6	121.934	Czechia	C2	0.704889
7	131.14	Germany	C2	0.696507
8	133.521	Denmark	C2	0.693436
10	99.9969	Spain	C2	0.651615
11	101.797	Finland	C2	0.65308
12	111.156	France	C2	0.70439
14	101.419	Hungary	C2	0.69551
15	130.494	Ireland	C2	0.701196
17	110.553	Italy	C2	0.700496
18	120.232	Lithuania	C2	0.69575
20	125.615	Malta	C2	0.697952
21	115.816	Netherlands	C2	0.706628
25	111.944	Sweden	C2	0.698317
27	109.884	Slovakia	C2	0.662482
28	93.2339	United Kingdom	C2	0.579607

Emissioni nell'aria da polveri sottili

Rank	Country	2021	Rank	Country	2021
1	Switzerland	134,60	17	Spain	100,00
2	Denmark	133,52	18	Luxembourg	95,83
3	Germany	131,14	19	United Kingdom	93,23
4	Ireland	130,49	20	Slovenia	87,40
5	Austria	127,80	21	Norway	84,61
6	Malta	125,62	22	Croatia	76,30
7	Czechia	121,93	23	Romania	70,64
8	Lithuania	120,23	24	Greece	66,03
9	Netherlands	115,82	25	Iceland	63,56
10	Sweden	111,94	26	Bulgaria	62,71
11	France	111,16	27	Poland	53,98
12	Italy	110,55	28	Estonia	35,35
13	Slovakia	109,88	29	Cyprus	30,58
14	Belgium	109,25	30	Latvia	0,00
15	Finland	101,80	31	Portugal	0,00
16	Hungary	101,42	32	Serbia	0,00

Emissioni nell'aria da polveri sottili

Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Luxembourg</i>	24,85	35,00	16	<i>Netherlands</i>	6,96	6,39
2	<i>Poland</i>	13,50	33,35	17	<i>Finland</i>	4,75	4,90
3	<i>Croatia</i>	14,21	22,88	18	<i>Denmark</i>	5,80	4,54
4	<i>Lithuania</i>	19,93	19,87	19	<i>Slovenia</i>	3,08	3,65
5	<i>Slovakia</i>	16,94	18,22	20	<i>Germany</i>	3,11	2,43
6	<i>Romania</i>	10,72	17,88	21	<i>Switzerland</i>	3,00	2,28
7	<i>Norway</i>	12,08	16,66	22	<i>Greece</i>	0,42	0,64
8	<i>Czechia</i>	15,62	14,69	23	<i>France</i>	0,53	0,48
9	<i>Iceland</i>	8,05	14,50	24	<i>Malta</i>	-1,65	-1,29
10	<i>Italy</i>	9,71	9,62	25	<i>United Kingdom</i>	-1,32	-1,39
11	<i>Sweden</i>	9,59	9,37	26	<i>Hungary</i>	-2,03	-1,97
12	<i>Austria</i>	10,33	8,79	27	<i>Bulgaria</i>	-9,30	-12,91
13	<i>Belgium</i>	8,77	8,73	28	<i>Cyprus</i>	-9,62	-23,92
14	<i>Ireland</i>	10,47	8,72	29	<i>Serbia</i>	-8,75	-100,00
15	<i>Spain</i>	6,79	7,29				